

Joule heating to temperatures significantly exceeding room temperature could have occurred in recently reported hybrid perovskite transistors.

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Studies of thin-film transistors (TFTs) based on novel semiconducting materials, including, e.g., halide perovskites, organic semiconductors, monolayer materials, nanowire and nanocrystal arrays, are important for our understanding of the basic charge transport properties of these materials and developing applications.¹ However, in a number of recent publications, rather extreme biasing regimes were used in TFT measurements of delicate materials, in which potential issues related to very high local current densities or Joule heating remained unaddressed.²

The video (accessible via the link in Ref. ³ or attached file) and **Fig. 1** below show the results of a test imitating the biasing conditions of hybrid perovskite TFTs recently reported by H. Zhu *et al.*⁴ In order to closely reproduce measurement conditions of H. Zhu *et al.*⁴, we used a commercially available thin-film chip resistor (a metal film deposited on a small, flat ceramic substrate, size 0402) of resistance $R = 1 \text{ k}\Omega$. The area of the resistive film is comparable to the channel area, A , of the reported TFTs ($A = \text{channel length} \times \text{channel width} = 0.2 \times 1 \text{ mm}^2$). In our setup (**Fig. 1a** and video in Ref. ³), the resistor is firmly glued film-down to an ultra-smooth oxide surface of a silicon wafer similar to that used by H. Zhu *et al.* (a 0.6 mm-thick single-crystal Si wafer with a thermal SiO_2), ensuring a good thermal contact between the resistive film and the substrate. The resistor is connected to a power source with 44 AWG tin-coated copper wires that are soldered directly to the resistor's contact pads on the sides of the chip (such that they do not interfere with making a good physical contact of the resistive film with the wafer). To induce Joule heating of the resistive film very similar to that of the perovskite TFTs in H. Zhu *et al.*, we have applied the same *power density* as the maximum power density, $P_{\text{max}} = 200 \text{ W}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$, applied by the authors in their perovskite TFTs during the measurements (the leftmost data points of the transfer curve in **Fig. 1c** of H. Zhu *et al.*).⁴ P_{max} is defined as the product of the source-drain voltage and the maximum source-drain current, divided by the channel area:⁵

$$P_{\max} = \frac{V_{SD} \cdot I_{SD}^{\max}}{A}. \quad (1)$$

During the experiment, we imaged our sample with an infrared thermal camera Micro-Epsilon ThermoIMAGER TIM640 (15 degrees, $f = 41.5$ mm, default emissivity 0.880) capturing a video of *in-situ* temperature distribution along the surface of the sample and the substrate (all exposed non-metallic surfaces are imaged). Based on emissivities of the imaged materials, we estimate the accuracy of our temperature measurements as $\sim 10\%$.

A frame of the video, showing an example of the temperature map when the resistor is biased, is presented in **Fig. 1b**. The temporal temperature profiles, $T(t)$, calculated from the video in Ref. ³ are shown in **Fig. 1c**. The temperature is calculated in the three regions outlined with the white rectangles in **Fig. 1b**: the resistor itself (black curve), a small region of the substrate close to the resistor (red curve), and a region of the substrate far from the resistor (green curve). It can be seen from **Fig. 1c** and the video in Ref. ³ that right after the excitation current is applied, the resistor heats up very quickly, reaching temperatures well above 100 °C in a fraction of a second (at a rate of ~ 350 °C·s⁻¹) and heating up further to > 150 °C in seconds. The temperature of the substrate (Si wafer) also increases rapidly and significantly: its temperature near the sample goes up to ~ 80 °C (red curve in **Fig. 1c**). These observations confirm an excellent thermal contact between the resistive film and the Si wafer in our experiment. Even if we conservatively assume that the thermal contact in our test was poor, improving it can only lead to an even higher temperature of the substrate, thus suggesting that heating of the perovskite film in the measurements under high bias performed by H. Zhu *et al.* must indeed be very significant.

This demonstration shows that during the TFT measurements described by H. Zhu *et al.*, the temperature of the perovskite thin film might easily increase from room temperature all the way to > 150 °C. Thus, while the paper explicitly portrays these measurements as a reproducible, room-temperature, continuous (*steady-state*) TFT operation with the stated mobilities, in reality, their perovskite film is likely out of thermal equilibrium with the setup/ambient, and this effect must be especially strong in the most important high-current region of the transfer curves. Obviously, such biasing conditions cannot be considered safe or reliable when studying semiconductors whose properties are expected to be temperature dependent. Furthermore, issues of possible material's degradation, parameter drift, or *in-situ* irreversible modifications (due to, e.g., ionic drifts), known to occur in perovskites under such measurement conditions, could have an impact on the reported results and conclusions. Indeed, compared to conventional inorganic semiconductors, (hybrid) metal-halide perovskites are soft-lattice materials,^{6,7} not expected to be very structurally⁸ and morphologically⁹ stable at $T > 150$ °C. Although these films are usually annealed at up to 100 °C at the stage of fabrication, applying a very strong electric

bias simultaneously with unintended heating in TFT measurements can make a difference. Indeed, the average longitudinal electric field applied by the authors in the transfer curve measurements (**Fig. 1c** of H. Zhu *et al.*⁴) is very high, $2 \text{ kV}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$. Given the fact that these are saturation regime measurements, the local electric field in the pinch-off region of the channel could be even higher. It remains unclear how the detrimental effects of possible material's modification and degradation, and especially a very likely non-room-temperature operation could have been avoided in steady-state continuous measurements reported by the authors. None of these issues were investigated or even mentioned in the paper.

Figure 1. Thermal imaging of the local temperature distribution of a resistive film on a substrate under biasing conditions emulating the measurements of perovskite TFTs by H. Zhu *et al.*⁴ (a) A photograph of a thin-film resistor chip thermally anchored to a square piece of silicon wafer and wired to a power source. (b) A screenshot of the thermal video taken right after the device has been powered up (the higher the local temperature, the brighter the color). The full video recorded with Micro-Epsilon ThermoIMAGER is available elsewhere.³ (c) Time profiles, $T(t)$, calculated from the thermal video in the three regions outlined with the white rectangles in panel **b**: the resistor itself (black), a small region of the substrate close to the resistor (red), and a region of the substrate far from the resistor (green). Temperature is averaged over the area of each region. An electric bias generating the same power density as that used in perovskite TFTs by H. Zhu *et al.* (i.e., $P_{\text{max}} = 200 \text{ W/cm}^2$) is applied at the time marked by the vertical red dotted line and turned off at ~ 22 s. The rate of the sample's heating ($\sim 350 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$) has been determined by a linear fit of the initial heating region of the black curve (near the red dotted line).

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